

MACHINE TOOLS BROUGHT TO THE TERRITORY OF BUKHARA FROM FOREIGN COUNTRIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRODUCTION AND TRADE

Haydarov Saifiddin

Doctoral student of the Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800267>

Annotation: In order to provide farmers and herdsmen with machines and equipment, the government of Bukhara purchased foreign equipment through German companies. 167 American machines bought from abroad arrived in Bukhara during the revolution (1920-1924) for the first time. 22 straw cutting machines and several machines - plows are lying on the road" - reports "Bukhara Akhbori" newspaper (1923).

Key words: Botumi, Kogon and Karmana,

Straw cutters and machine plows were delivered to the territory of the Republic of Bukhara in the fall of 1923. This made it possible to finish the field work on time, easing the manual labor of the farmers several times during the harvesting period. Delivery of goods from the Republic of Bukhara to Germany in cooperation with the "Russian-Bukhara Shareholding Company", "Russian State Trade Branch", "State Trade Branch" of the Bukhara Council of People's Supervisors, etc., is delivered to Botumi (Georgia's Black Sea port) in batches of 10,000 pounds, and from there loaded onto steamers of German companies. , taken to Europe. Sometimes, he bought products for German companies from the special stores of the Moscow trade branch that trade in black leather.

Medicines, hospital equipment, syringes and needles began to be brought to Bukhara from Germany. "The trading company started sending cotton to Moscow. 30 wagons of cotton were sent from Bukhara, Kogon and Karmana. It was planned to send 200 wagons by October 15, 1923. The state trading branch started collecting wool from Karshi, Karki, Chorjoi and Bukhara regions. These days, 10 wagons of wool are being sent from Chorjoi and Bukhara. Some of these goods are intended to be exported through Russia," reports say.

The purpose of receiving medicine and hospital equipment from this country in exchange for goods from Bukhara that reached Germany is the need to treat diseases such as rishta (under-the-skin worms), malaria, "Bukhara fever" inherited from the Emirate period among the people of Bukhara, as well as to establish modern hospitals and equip them with equipment. the need to provide with The populist leader F. Khojaev agreed to receive first of all medicines and hospital equipment in exchange for goods from Bukhara sent to Germany. He was

the leader of the government who deeply understood that the main wealth of the Republic is the health of the people, and he loved his people and his country.

"All kinds of medicines and hospital equipment bought from Germany have arrived. Several more hospital equipment and 1,500 needles (syringes) are expected to arrive these days." Between February and November 1923, 4 carloads of hospital equipment and medicines worth 200,000 soums were brought to the Republic of Bukhara from Germany. In order to expand trade relations and arrange settlements, the German trading company signed an agreement with the Bukhara State Bank and established mutual cooperation. Medicinal plant-confectionery trade played an important role in trade relations between the Republic of Bukhara and Germany.

It is known that licorice is a healing medicinal plant that grows in the deserts and deserts of Zarafshan oasis and cures various diseases such as licorice, milk thistle, gozpanja and tamarisk. So, it was natural that sweetmeat would be of interest to German industrialists, who were experts in the production of medicines. Officials of the republic have calculated that the licorice plant is widespread in the territory of the Republic of Bukhara and that it is a free gift of nature, and that trade with it can bring great benefits. According to the sources, two German companies "Schroeder and his partners" and "Germany-Black Sea" companies were interested in sweet candy and its price and made offers to take it to Germany.

The Russian-Bukhara-German joint-stock companies each set up an initial capital turnover of 30,000 gold soums for the sale of sweetmeats. The government of the republic, thinking about the prospects of the sweetmeat trade, planned to create sweetmeat plantations together with the cotton fields. In Chorjoi region, a special sweetmeat pressing factory was established and "Sherinmiya Company" was established. In a short time, 200,000 poods of sweet potato seeds and roots were collected at the plant. Chorjoi sweet potato factory pressed half a wagon of sweet potato every day, and in a short time, 10 wagons of sweet potato worth 20,000 gold soums were prepared for shipment to Germany. At the end of 1923, 10,000 pounds of sweetmeat and 60 wagons of cotton bales were sent to Germany through the ports of Batumi and Astrakhan.

When Bukhara sweetmeat reached Germany, a number of companies opened enterprises that process it and buy medicines. This made it possible to provide jobs to some of the German workers who were in a difficult economic situation in those years. Many letters were received from a number of companies in Berlin and Hamburg, Germany, aimed at determining the price of candy.

Another issue concerns the activity of the Bukhara trade and industry companies with the "Sinkup" company in Germany on the sale and purchase of intestines. Initially, it was agreed that 25 percent of the profit from the intestines exported to Germany would go to the Bukhara bank. In the summer of 1923, 25,000 intestines were sent to Germany via Bukhara, Baku and Moscow for processing. In order to develop trade relations in this field in the Republic of Bukhara, the "Rus-Bukhara Joint Stock Company" and the "Bukhara Trade-Industry Company" established a special "Intestinal Preparation Company" and its system was approved. The fact that the first intestine factory was built in Bukhara is an indication that the intestine trade is not without profit for the young republic.

In short, the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic has followed a path that will be a historical lesson in economic cooperation and mutual trade relations with Germany in its short historical period. Unfortunately, after 1924, the promising plans of economic cooperation relations turned into a mirage.

References:

1. Mavlanov O'. Ancient trade routes of Central Asia. - T., "Universitet", 2009.
2. Muhammedova S. Musa Saidjonov's activity in the field of economics in the USSR. History of Uzbekistan. 2014, No. 4, pp. 82-90.
3. Ntiya, Ekanem Otu. Soviet-Nigerian relations 1960 - 1985. K.i.n. - M., 1989.
4. Nuritdinov T. About the history of the economic cooperation of the USSR with Germany. History of Uzbekistan. 2010, No. 2, pp. 31-36.
5. Oleynichenko G.N. Soviet-Indian relations (1954-1956). K.i.n. - M., 1958
6. Rashidov U. Bukhara People's Republic (1920 - 1924). "Bukhara" publishing house, 2003.
7. Saidov Sh.D. Foreign relations and trade union of the USSR (1920 - 1924). K.i.n. - T., 2003 g. AN. R. Uz.

